

Energy storage for reaching 100% CO₂ free and 100% RES – preliminary case study for Romania

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Abstract—The paper analyses energy production and consumption recorded for the Romanian power system in selected days and shows how storage resources can mitigate situations with 100% CO₂ free and 100% RES respectively, by simulating through scaling the production based on these new scenarios. The study assumes a similar power exchange with neighbors, to avoid drastic network reinforcement and to improve regional auto-consumption, thus improving resilience. Based on the studied days, the storage level, needed to maintain acceptable tie-lines cumulated power exchanges, is analyzed in terms of KPIs such as the total need of storage capacity in GWh, the power to energy ratio, and PV power to storage energy ratio. The results suggest similar requirements with the today trends in PV and storage pairing, thus inferring the feasibility of 100% CO₂ as well as 100% RES in the Romanian power system as being possible from the energy balancing point of view.

Index Terms-- Storage, energy systems, renewable energy, resilience, sustainability, KPI

I. INTRODUCTION

Storage is the missing link in the energy ecosystem. From more than one hundred years the rule in AC systems was that energy need to be consumed in the moment it is produced. This asked for solutions to ensure in the same time the equilibrium of active power and the stability of voltage. For this, classic generation is modulated to produce the needed consumption and pump storage was till now the only additional bulk instrument in the area.

Technology is giving today however a signal for a massive change of paradigm. After tenths of years in the research area, storage technology is enlarging now the niches and finally starts to become mainstream. It comes as a synergetic need from both electrical vehicles asking for cost-effective batteries solution as well from the stationary applications which request solutions for the intermittent production of renewables. The renewables sources (RES) became so cheap that they do not need anymore subsidies but beat classic production, as shown in recent developments [1]. However, this cheap renewable

energy is intermittent and need to be accommodated in the grid. The generation-consumption equality asks then for various measures, and curtailment is one of the final solutions for the TSOs.

But all these difficult conditions for operation have now one general solution: the ubiquitous electrical distributed energy storage, at all possible levels: at production, grid and domestic level. The paper analyses the way how storage is changing the business as usual (BaU) in a way which allows that production and final consumption do not need any more to be always in equilibrium, as being buffered by distributed storage, thus changing the paradigm from more than a century.

The paper is considering latest achievements and highlights the vision for short and medium term future of the storage applications, for serving needs such as balancing through storage, RES curtailment avoidance, peak shaving, electrical vehicles charging, microgrids and prosumers proliferation bringing increased system stability and user resilience.

The study selects specific days in Romanian power system, with different ratios of PV and wind production. Very high penetration of RES is now a scenario which starts to be considered by European policy, aiming for a 100% CO₂ free situation in 2050 [2] - which mean a mix of only RES and nuclear power. There are already more ambitious aims in California and Hawaii (100% RES in 2045, including EVs) or new milestones in Queensland, Australia (50% RES in 2030), or in smart cities such as San Diego, California (100% RES in 2035, without counting EVs).

The existing RES penetration in Europe differs from country to country. In Romania is already reached 24%, which is planned in fact for 2023. But with the new situation of falling prices to PV, wind and storage equipment, with the new global rethinking of the targets, 100% CO₂ situation need already to be considered. Today TSOs are considering mainly two ways of coping with such dramatic renewables penetration: improve flexibility and cross-border exchange

and ultimately control with curtailments when production does not meet consumption and when critical lines or nodes exceed the normal operation parameters and exchange of energy with neighbourhoods, within a pan-European market. But even if part of the energy which is not consumed inside the national borders is exported, a high share of national (or regional) self-production is necessary for reasons of system stability and resilience. We are investigating how storage can help a high rate of national self-consumption, by analyzing the current power production and consumption and by scaling through simulation an increased RES penetration.

II. A 100% CO₂ FREE AND STORAGE SCENARIO

Fig. 1 shows a typical summer day of production and consumption in Romanian power system, with moderate RES, corresponding to the date of 08.06.2017.

Figure 1. Production, consumption and power exchange in Romanian power system on 08.06.2017.

By calculation the daily data we determine key parameters which are presented later in table 3, where different days and scenarios are presented synthetically. The calculations are based on public available real-time measurements obtained from the Transelectrica transparency webpage [3].

The following formula apply:

$$E_r = \max \{ E_{Balance+} / P_{Cons}, E_{Balance-} / P_{Cons} \}$$

$$R_{E/P} = E_{BAT} / P_{BAT}$$

$$R_{E/P_{PV}} = E_{BAT} / P_{MAX_{PV}}$$

where exchange ratio E_r and $E_{Balance+}$ and $E_{Balance-}$ are exchanged energies with neighbours in each direction, E_{BAT} is the total battery capacity [GWh], P_{BAT} is the battery output power and $P_{MAX_{PV}}$ is the peak PV power in a day.

The basic situation shows percentages of production compared with the total daily consumption of 158.7 GWh. The wind and solar (PV) stochastic production cover 7.74 and 1.61% of the total consumption (9.35% in total), while traditional hydro energy stands for 34.27% in this particular day. Storage is not considered in this basic scenario, as Romania does not have neither pump storage facility nor new technology of distributed storage based on Li-Ion, redox or other new technology. The energy exchange has a total value of -4.9 GWh, which mean only 3.1% of the total energy. This represents the total power exchange with the neighbourhoods, which is one of the methods listed for accommodating high

the RES penetration: energy in the national boundaries is at certain periods exported (+4.8%), or imported (-1.7%).

The maximum power on import is 692 MW and on export 1100 MW, these values giving information about the total needed capacity for the tie lines, which has to be lower than the Net Transfer Capacity (NTC).

Moreover for the hydro energy, which is considered to be dispatchable, it is synthetized an average power over the day $P_{HYDRO} = 2266$ MW and an energy of plus and minus is considered for upper and lower values, as a sort of balancing energy which is delivered over the day, to give a performance index of the hydro flexibility used in this particular day. Coal, gas and nuclear count for 29.9%, 8.5% and 20.6%.

For a 100% CO₂ free and storage scenario in Romanian power system we simulate by scaling high the RES penetration and we completely phase-out coal and gas production, by still keeping the nuclear production as it is now, while consumption boosts with 10%, as per Table 1.

TABLE I. INCREASE OF RES AND PHASE-OUT CO₂ DEPENDENT PRODUCTION

Simulation factors	Today factor	Sim.factor:
Consumpt.factor K_cons	100%	110%
Wind factor K_wnd	100%	320%
PV factor K_pv	100%	1600%
Biomass factor K_bio	100%	300%
Hydro factor K_hyd	100%	110%
Coal factor K_coal	100%	0%
Gas power factor K_gas	100%	0%
Nuclear factor K_nucl	100%	100%

The factors have been engineered until the 100% CO₂ free daily production meets the daily consumption of 174.5GWh. The table shows that it is needed a factor of 16x (1600%) for PV production and of 3.2x for wind production, while hydro can also increase with 10% from today situation. The K_coal and K_gas are now zero, in order to simulate that these technologies are completely phased out.

Fig. 2 shows the evolution of the power for production and consumption over the day. In this situation, the daily production and consumption are presented in Table III.

Figure 2. Production, consumption and power exchange on 08.06.2017, in a CO₂ free scenario.

Wind and PV count now for 46%, which is around five times as has been before, and that we have a net exchange with neighbourhood of 9.17% and -9.32%, which means around 16 GWh on each direction. The maximum power on

import is 2354 MW and on export -3758 MW, these values giving information about the total needed capacity for the tie lines, much higher than before. A balancing equivalent of 6 GWh is provided by hydro facilities, which is according to the 110% increase of hydro power in the simulation.

A third situation is considered by using storage inside the national grid in such a volume and allocation over commercial hours such that the neighbourhood exchange power remains in the boundaries of the first scenario (the today situation). In this situation, the daily production, consumption and storage program profile are presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Production, consumption and power exchange on 08.06.2017, in a CO2 free scenario with storage resources.

The net exchange with neighbourhood is -2.8% and +2.7%, which means around 4.7 GWh in each direction.

The maximum power on import is 833 MW and on export 1758 MW for short time, these values being near the range of the current total needed capacity for the tie lines in the studied day. It is important to see that storage needs are of 14.8 GWh and that the power for storage is maximum 2000 MW, which brings a factor of 7.5 / 1 between power and energy, higher than the usual requests of 4 / 1 or 5 / 1 already asked in California or Australia. For simplifying the simulation, the balance between charging and discharging the batteries is zero. For considering the sub-unitary efficiency of batteries, less discharge power can be considered in the whole day.

III. 100% RES AND STORAGE IN ROMANIAN POWER SYSTEM

In this section the analysis goes further and considers that nuclear power production is also completely phased out, as in the Californian ambition. In this situation, the daily equality between production and consumption has been reached with 25x PV and 4x wind energy. Other combinations can also meet the condition. The power evolution of production, consumption and the neighbourhood exchange (on tie-lines) are presented in Fig. 4.

The used factors for RES are presented in Table II. It can be seen an increase of the neighbourhood exchange to approximate 24 GWh in both directions. Tie-lines support in this situation maximum 3572 MW during import and -6200 MW during export of energy, much higher than in the 100% CO2 free scenario without storage resources.

As has been simulated in the 100% CO2 free scenario, a storage resource will be considered also in this 100% RES scenario. Various schedules can be considered, based on selected or optimized situations.

Figure 4. Production, consumption and power exchange on 08.06.2017, 100% RES scenario

TABLE II. 100% RES PRODUCTION FACTORS

Simulation factors	Today factor	Sim.factor:
Consumpt.factor K_cons	100%	110%
Wind factor K_wnd	100%	400%
PV factor K_pv	100%	2500%
Biomass factor K_bio	100%	300%
Hydro factor K_hyd	100%	110%
Coal factor K_coal	100%	0%
Gas power factor K_gas	100%	0%
Nuclear factor K_nucl	100%	0%

The simulation targets as in the previous situation a reduction of power exchange with the tie-lines which is similar with the today situation. Other combinations can be subject of future work. Fig. 5 shows the power evolution of all components when using also storage resources.

Figure 5. Production, consumption, storage and power exchange on 08.06.2017, in a 100% RES (no nuclear) scenario.

The simulation can reach a tie-lines power exchange slightly higher than in basic case of today by adding a storage resource of 4 GW in power and 20.8 GWh of energy, which brings a ratio of around 5 / 1 for energy versus power, similar with new requests in Australia regarding PV and associated storage (900 MW PV and 4 GWh storage, [4]).

The tie-lines power are in this latest situation 1512 MW for import and -2200 MW for export. Lower power values on tie-lines would need even higher nominal power of the storage resources, for absorbing or generating power.

IV. OTHER DAYS, WITH DIFFERENT PV AND WIND CONDITIONS

For analyzing more situations, another day has been chosen, with much lower wind production but with high PV

production, namely 29.05.2017. As the power evolution can be seen in Fig. 6, the maximum exchange power is 1104 MW for import and 942 MW for export and the wind, PV and hydro productions are 3.26%, 4.35% and respectively 33.3%. The power system has in this particular day only one nuclear group in function, which delivers around 10% of the country need. The day has high PV production (4.3% energy and 0.78 GW max power) and moderate wind production (3.3%).

Figure 6. Production, consumption, and power exchange on 29.05.2017

For having 100% CO₂ free production, the condition of equality for production and consumption has been reached with scaling factors of 2.5x, 12x and 1.1x for wind, PV and hydro, at a daily consumption (ECONS) of 164 GWh. The simulation shows that the import/export reaches 4050 and -5080 MW of power, which ask for storage resources in order to reduce exchange power and to preserve a good national self-consumption. The energy balance need around 31 GWh of imported and exported energy, which stands as an equivalent tie-line-battery. The power evolutions is presented in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Production, consumption, storage and power exchange on 29.05.2017, in 100% CO₂ free scenario

The target of reducing power exchange towards the today situation has been reached with a cumulated battery energy (ESTOR) of 26 GWh, with a maximum power (PSTROR,M) of 4 GW. The total exchange of power is 1200 MW and -1585 MW for import and export, keeping the regime near to the today tie-lines connectivity. It needs an attention the fact that 77.9 GWh of daily PV production (EPV) having a peak (PVmax) of around 9 GW can be mitigated with only 31 GWh of storage. This means that if any new PV installation will have associated an energy storage which can absorb for 3.4 hours the PV nominal power, the system is able to have a neighbor exchange ratio E_r less than 10%.

The last analyzed day is in winter (23.01.2017), in low RES conditions, when cumulated PV and wind have only 3% of the total consumption. The needed scaling for 100% CO₂ free is 5.5x for wind and 55x for PV, which is a huge scaling.

V. RESULTS OVERVIEW

Table III gives the main figures for all three studied cases, from sections III and IV. It shows that base load of nuclear brings advantages and that the necessary storage is less. Moreover, the low wind / low solar shows that such days need to be accommodated with other means, such as longer storage technologies or much higher neighbor connectivity.

In the table, Exch_P+ means imported power and Esch_P- means exported power. The values are inputs for assessing the total tie-lines capacity. It shows that the solutions without storage need much higher neighborhood capacity and that the energy exchanged is also much higher, the neighbors acting as buffer or like a huge storage device. Storg.P is the total power output of the storage resources.

It has been not analyzed any topology constraint inside the country because it has been considered that most of the RES are distributed, which is quite applicable with PV production, and that the storage resources are also distributed, as a possible change of paradigm comparing with traditional pump storage facilities, which need additional transport lines and potential bottlenecks. Some system enforcements may be however needed at least for the wind production, which is more concentrated in specific zones, however an appropriate storage rollout may decrease this need as well. Each day has been analyzed separately, in order to give a first image on the dimension of PV/wind production and storage needed for each case. More comprehensive approaches will be done in further work, also considering longer term storage, which can change for instance the need of PV capacity in the winter time (similar to the winter day case). Additional cases and longer term situations have been not addressed in this study, however it is expected that the results may bring either additional need of storage and/or addition need for enforcing the grid. The national self-consumption ratio higher than 90% (exchange ratio $E_r < 10\%$) is a balanced approach, as there is no guarantee of high complementarity of RES production between countries, especially related to the PV production.

A comprehensive analysis would need a complete year assessment, however for typical days having abundant renewables, usually encountered in more than half of the yearly period, the 100% CO₂ and sometime 100% RES is feasible. In order to enlarge the analysis, additional days have been similarly simulated: 02.08.2016, 10.09.2016, 15.11.2016, 17.03.2017, 22.04.2017 and the total needed storage ESTOR and max PV production PVMAX in a CO₂ free scenario was: 40/10.1, 42/10.3, 19/5.2, 29/7.7, 26/7.6 [GWh_{storage} / GW_{max_PV}], showing that applying this simulation on separate days the Romanian power system needs usually up to 45 GWh of storage.

An important KPI is the RE/P_PV ratio between the needed storage capacity (GWh) and the maximum PV power (GW) – to be correlated with the total nominal power of PVs, factor which did not exceeded 4.1 in our selected days.

TABLE III. USUAL, 100% CO2 FREE AND 100% RES SCENARIO (SIMULATION ON 3 DAYS: 08.6.2017, 29.05.2017 AND 23.01.2017)

Description	Crt. Sit. 08.06.2017	100 % CO2 free	100% CO2 free+ storage	100% RES	100% RES + storage	Crt. Sit. 23.01.2017	100% CO2 free	100% CO2 free+ storage	Crt. Sit. 29.05.2017	100 % CO2 free	100% CO2 free+ storage	100% RES, nuclear	100% RES + storage
Day type	Moderate solar and wind (08.06.2017)					Low PV+wnd (23.01.2017)			High solar (29.05.2017)				
Wind ratio	7.74%	3.2x = 22.5%		4x = 28.1%		2.1%	5.5x = 10.5%		3.3%	2.5x = 7.4%		3x = 8.9%	
E _{WIND} [GWh]	12.3	39.3		49.1		4	21.8		4.8	12.1		14.6	
PV [%]	1.61%	16x = 23.5%		25x = 36.7%		0.93%	52x = 44.1%		4.3%	12x = 47.5%		14.2x = 56.1%	
E _{PV} [GWh]	2.56	40.9		64		1.7	91.9		6.5	77.9		92.2	
PVmax[GW]	0.37	5.9		9.25		0.34	17.6		0.78	9.4		11.1	
Hydro	34.3%	1.1x = 34.3%		1.1x = 34.3%		27.1%	1.1x = 27.6%		33.4%	1.1x = 33.3%		1.1x = 33.4%	
Nuclear [%]	20.6%	1x = 18.8%		-		17.8%	1x = 16.1%		11.1	1x		-	
Coal+gas [%]	38.4%	-		-		52.6%	-		43.9	-		-	
E _{CONS} [GWh]	158.7	1.1x = 174.5		1.1x = 174.5		189.2	1.1x = 208.1		149.2	1.1x = 164.1		1.1x = 164.1	
P_{EXCH+}[GW]	0.69	2.3	0.83	3.5	1.5	0.14	4.01	2.45	1.1	4.1	1.20	4.7	1.4
E _{EXCH+} [GWh]	2.7	16	4.5	24	6.9	0.1	47.6	21.0	9.86	31	6.4	37.5	7.6
P_{EXCH-}[GW]	-1.10	-3.7	-1.7	-6.2	-2.2	-0.64	-10.5	-4.9	-0.94	-5.1	-1.58	-6.1	-1.6
E _{EXCH-} [GWh]	-7.7	-16	-4.8	-24.5	-7.3	-4.0	-47.2	-19.5	-4.58	-30.5	-6	-37.3	7.4
Exch.ratio Er	4.83%	9%	2.8%	14%	4.2%	2.1%	25%	10.1%	6.6%	18.9	3.9%	22.8%	4.6%
P _{STORM} [GW]	-	-	2	-	4	-	-	8	-	-	4	-	4.5
E_{STOR}[GWh]	-	-	14.8	-	20.8	-	-	42	-	-	26	-	32
R _{EP}	-	-	7	-	5.2	-	-	5	-	-	6.5	-	7.1
R _{EP PV}	-	-	2.5	-	2.3	-	-	3.1	-	-	2.8	-	2.9

It shows that today trends in PV installed power in pair with storage capacity with a 3 to 5 ratio, which is currently a trend in 2017, are attainable targets in near future for all RES developments.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Integrating high share of renewables is a difficult task for TSOs. Fortunately, the new solutions based on distributed storage can change drastically the paradigm of integrating RES. The paper analyzed specific days with the evolution of consumption and production for the Romanian power system. The following situations have been compared: the situation with the current mix of generation, simulated situation with 100% CO2 free (nuclear generation is still present) and 100% RES - without or with storage. In the simulations it has been considered similar or slightly increased energy exchange with neighborhood, such that tie-lines are kept as usual while resilience is enforced based on national self-consumption.

The results in terms of storage need and tie-line power exchange are summarized in the table III. Two days have been analyzed and detailed in both terms of CO2 free and RES and a third has been analyzed only in terms of CO2 free situation, because even this scenario gave an unacceptable high scaling of today RES. Additional days have been analyzed, with similar results. It is obvious that some days need a different approach, meaning that medium to long term storage is needed, subject to be assessed in further work.

It shows also that 100% CO2 free and even 100% RES are achievable with today technology and will become economically viable on large scale in the next years, somewhere around years 2020-2025, making the today political ambitions for clean energy in 2050 a possible reality in 2035-2040, a good measure for reducing the temperature raise to 1.5-2 degrees till 2050, target of the Paris agreement.

With these first analysis, a total battery distributed capacity of 35-45 GWh energy and 5-7 GW power, with 10-12 GW of available solar power and 6-8 GW of available

wind power can ensure 100% CO2 and even 100% RES in most of the year.

The future power system design to accommodate these requests will need many measures to be taken in parallel: large PV distributed deployments, moderate wind parks deployments in appropriate places, moderate reinforcements in the national grid, especially to accommodate wind farms and small reinforcements in the neighborhood connectivity, to accept short term exchange of higher power, high penetration of microgrids and proliferation of prosumers.

The work intends to bring a preliminary outlook on the RES integration problems and to show the degree of storage needs, as an entry point for more complex analysis regarding balancing the produced, consumed and stored energy, thus mitigating today problems such as curtailment of excess power in high RES penetration situations. Other technical aspects, e.g. medium and long term storage technologies or reduction of inertia will be developed in future studies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Lowest-Ever Solar Price Bid, (2.42¢/kWh) Dropped In Abu Dhabi, From: <https://cleantechnica.com/2016/09/20/lowest-ever-solar-price-bid-2-42%C2%A2kwh-dropped-abu-dhabi-jinkosolar-marubeni-score/>
- [2] The "Winter Package" of the European Commission. Online: <http://www.europe-infos.eu/the-winter-package-of-the-european-commission>
- [3] http://www.transelectrica.ro/widget/web/tel/sen-harta/-/harta_WAR_SENOperareHartaportlet, accessed during 2016-2017
- [4] K. Pichkerel, Residential Solar Energy Storage Market to Reach 900 MW in 2018, Solar Builder Magazine, November 12, 2014.